

Synthesis and Characterization of Some Neutral and Mixed Ligand Adducts of Titanium(IV) Chloride with N-, O-, S- Donor Ligands and Sulphadruugs and Evaluation of the Plant Growth Regulating Potentiality of the Sulphadruug Adducts

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Hitherto unknown eighteen neutral and mixed ligand adducts of $TiCl_4$ with several N-, O-, S-donor ligands and sulphadruugs have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, ir and pmr spectral data. The efficiency of the sulphadruug adducts on the growth of *Pisum sativum* plant has also been evaluated.

As a part of our continued interest on the coordination compounds of MX_4^{1-2} and also keeping in view the biological importance of the sulphadruugs^{3,4}, we have isolated thirteen neutral adducts of $TiCl_4$ of the general formula $TiCl_4.nL$ [$n=1$ or 2 ; $L=\beta$ -, γ -picoline (β -, γ -pic), diethanolamine (DEA), bipyridyl-N-oxide ($BipyO_2$), 1-methyl-2-piperidinone (1-Me-2-piper), dibutylsulfoxide (Bu_2SO), tetramethylthiouramdisulphide (TMIS), 2-aminothiazole (2-atz), benzothiazole (btz), 2-aminobenzothiazole (2-abtz); sulphadruugs: sulphaguanidine (SG), sulphadiazine (SD), sulphamethaxazole (SZ)] and five mixed ligand adducts of the formula $TiCl_4.LL'$ [L =dibutylsulfoxide (Bu_2SO), 2-aminothiazole (2-atz), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), benzothiazole (btz); L' = β -picoline (β -pic), 4-picoline-N-oxide (4-picO)]. All the compounds have been characterized through elemental analysis, molar conductance, ir and pmr spectral data. The adducts of the sulphadruugs have also been tested for their effect on the growth of the *Pisum sativum* plant. We are aware of one report describing the use of the thiocyanate derivatives of titanium(IV) as potential plant growth regulators⁵.

Experimental

$TiCl_4$ (B.D.H.) was used without further purification. The Lewis bases except $BipyO_2$ were procured commercially and the sulphadruugs were obtained from I. D. P. L. $BipyO_2$ was prepared by reported method⁶. The liquid bases were distilled and solids were recrystallized from suitable solvents before use.

The sulphadruug adducts were screened for their efficiency against the growth of the plant as described below.

The test plants were those of sweet peas (*Pisum sativum*) and the tests were done in multiplet using suitable control.

The complexes and sulphadruugs were dissolved in ethanol-water mixtures (250 ppm; 0.0624 g/250 ml).

Five sets of plants, each containing five, were grown in five containers. The first set was treated with water only. The remaining four sets were treated with solution of the two adducts ($TiCl_4.SG$; $TiCl_4.SD$) and the sulphadruugs (SG; SD). The treatment was done three times after 7 days intervals. The length and nodes of the plants were noted before and after each treatment.

Preparation of the adducts: The adducts were prepared by the direct interaction of the Lewis acid and Lewis bases in benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride or pet. ether using conventional ground glass apparatus. All manipulations were carried out in a dry box flushed with nitrogen. Physico chemical measurements were done as reported earlier¹.

(a) $TiCl_4.nL$: In a typical experiment 0.475 g (2.5 mmole) of $TiCl_4$ in benzene (20 ml) was mixed with 0.675 g (5 mmole) of benzothiazole in the same solvent (20 ml) with continuous stirring. The precipitated solid was filtered under nitrogen, washed with the same solvent, diethyl ether and dried *in vacuo*.

(b) $TiCl_4.n$ sulphadruug: 0.475 g (2.5 mmole) of $TiCl_4$ in carbon tetrachloride was mixed with a hot suspension of 0.535 g (2.5 mmole) of sulphaguanidine in the same solvent dropwise. After the complete addition of $TiCl_4$, the mixture was refluxed for 4-5 hr. The precipitate thus obtained

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR THE MOLECULAR ADDUCTS OF $TiCl_4 \cdot 2L$ AND $TiCl_4 \cdot LL'$

Sl. No.	Adducts	Colour	m.p (°C)	Analysis% : Found (Calcd.)				
				Ti	Cl	O	H	N
$TiCl_4 \cdot 2L$								
I	$L = \beta$ -pic	yellow	170	12.48 (12.74)	87.58 (87.72)	88.12 (88.84)	3.74 (3.75)	7.40 (7.45)
II	γ -pic	yellow	180	12.25 (12.74)	87.14 (87.72)	93.92 (88.84)	3.72 (3.75)	7.38 (7.45)
III	DEA*	light yellow	182-4	16.83 (16.25)	48.02 (48.10)	16.10 (16.29)	3.63 (3.75)	4.68 (4.76)
IV	BipyO ₂ *	white	>250	12.10 (12.68)	87.21 (87.52)	91.42 (81.78)	2.11 (2.13)	7.32 (7.41)
V	1-Me-2-piper	light yellow	80	11.08 (11.51)	88.99 (84.09)	94.58 (84.64)	5.32 (5.93)	6.61 (6.78)
VI	Bu ₃ SO	blackish yellow	129	9.02 (9.31)	27.56 (27.57)	87.90 (87.97)	7.01 (7.06)	—
VII	TMTS*	orange	176-8(d)	11.12 (11.13)	82.93 (82.96)	16.65 (16.75)	2.49 (2.81)	6.58 (6.51)
VIII	2-atz*	dark brown	177 8(d)	16.02 (16.53)	48.95 (48.92)	12.92 (12.43)	1.37 (1.39)	9.24 (9.67)
IX	Btz	red	210(d)	10.40 (10.41)	80.29 (80.82)	86.23 (86.55)	2.13 (2.19)	5.96 (6.09)
X	2-abtz	yellow	80-84	9.70 (9.77)	38.28 (38.93)	84.21 (84.32)	2.17 (2.47)	11.09 (11.43)
XI	SG	ash	140(d)	11.49 (11.86)	85.02 (85.10)	20.79 (20.81)	2.37 (2.50)	13.25 (13.87)
XII	SD	cream	165(d)	6.90 (6.94)	20.27 (20.54)	84.75 (84.80)	2.80 (2.92)	16.01 (16.28)
XIII	SZ*	pinkish violet	169-72(d)	10.25 (10.81)	82.01 (82.01)	27.00 (27.11)	2.45 (2.50)	9.82 (9.49)
$TiCl_4 \cdot LL'$								
XIV	$LL' = \text{DMSO}, \beta$ -pic	light yellow	124(d)	13.10 (13.27)	39.22 (39.29)	26.54 (26.62)	3.59 (3.63)	3.31 (3.33)
XV	Bu ₃ SO, β -pic	dark yellow	126 7(d)	10.69 (10.76)	31.66 (31.88)	37.75 (37.78)	5.62 (5.65)	3.15 (3.15)
XVI	Bu ₃ SO, btz	light red	91-3	9.25 (9.83)	29.08 (29.11)	36.42 (36.93)	4.70 (4.76)	2.76 (2.88)
XVII	btz, DMSO	light red	280	11.82 (11.88)	35.06 (35.19)	26.91 (26.82)	2.52 (2.75)	3.40 (3.48)
XVIII	2-atz, 4-picO	light brown	92-4	12.06 (12.01)	85.44 (85.54)	27.11 (27.09)	2.54 (2.78)	10.48 (10.58)

* Compounds correspond to 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

was filtered under nitrogen, washed with carbon tetrachloride, diethyl ether and dried *in vacuo*.

(c) $TiCl_4 \cdot LL'$: 0.475 g (2.5 mmole) of $TiCl_4$ in pet. ether (20 ml) was mixed with a solution of 0.4050 g (2.5 mmole) of Bu_3SO and 0.233 (2.5 mmole) of β -pic in the same solvent (20 ml) with constant stirring for 2 to 3 hr. The precipitated solid was filtered under nitrogen, washed with pet. ether, diethyl ether and dried *in vacuo*.

The complexes with their analytical data are listed in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the neutral adducts indicate 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry except TMTS, BipyO₂, 2-atz, DEA, SG, SZ adducts which correspond to 1 : 1 stoichiometry. All the complexes possess sharp melting points. They are coloured and moisture sensitive. The molar conductance (10^{-3} M soln) in methanol at 30° in the

range 0.57-4.78 mhos cm^2 mole⁻¹ indicates the non-electrolytic nature of the adducts.

IR spectra :

Adducts of N-donor ligands : The presence of N-bonded titanium is indicated by the following observations :

β -, γ -pic : An absorption due to antisymmetric vibrational mode at 1569 ± 18 cm^{-1} , totally symm. ring stretching at 1439 cm^{-1} and totally symm. ring breathing mode at 1000 cm^{-1} in the free picoline undergoing positive shift of the order of 30 to 50 cm^{-1} .

DEA : The $\nu C-N$ is shifted from 1105 cm^{-1} to 1090 cm^{-1} in the complexes⁶. The $\nu C-O$ frequency in the free ligand at 1025 cm^{-1} is shifted to 1030 cm^{-1} on complexation showing absence of bonding through the oxygen atom.

Adducts of O-donor ligands :

BipyO₂ : In the spectra of BipyO₂, an absorption of very strong intensity at 1264 cm^{-1} due to

TABLE 2—RELEVANT ABSORPTION BANDS (cm⁻¹) FOR THE MOLECULAR ADDUCTS OF TiCl₄.2L AND TiCl₄.LL/

Adducts*	Group	Frequency in free ligand	Frequency in adducts
I	CN	1569 ± 18	1625
II	CN	1569 ± 18	1635
III	C-N	1105	1090
	CO	1025	1030
IV	NO	1264	1227
	NO†	858	840
V	CO	1689	1618
VI	SO	947	900
VII	CN	1225	1238
	C=S	970	980
VIII	C=S	700	667
IX	asymCN + NCS†	1450	1460
X	NH ₂ †	1641	1637
	CN	1523	1595
XI	asymCN + NCS†	1444	1460
XI	NH ₂ †	1640	1610
XII	NH ₂ †	1640	1580
XIII	NH ₂ †	1610	1620
	CO	1150	1160
XIV	SO	1045	990
	CN	1550	1620
XV	SO	947	910
	CN	1550	1610
XVI	SO	947	910
	asymCN + NCS†	1450	1453
XVII	SO	1045	900
	asymCN + NCS†	1450	1468
XVIII	NO	1250	1210
	NH ₂ †	1620	1612

Note: All the vibrations are stretching modes except those marked with † which are bending modes.

* Sl. No. of the adducts are the same as in Table 1.

ν NO undergoes a significant negative shift ($-\Delta\nu$ NO=37 cm⁻¹) and absorption of strong intensity at 853 cm⁻¹ due to NO bending mode is shifted at 840 cm⁻¹. These observations indicate the presence of Ti←O bond^{1,10}.

1-Me-2-piper: The C=O frequency in free ligand appears at 1639 cm⁻¹ and is shifted to the lower region at 1613 cm⁻¹ on complexation indicating bonding through oxygen of the base¹¹.

Bu₂SO: In the spectrum of the free Bu₂SO an absorption of strong intensity at 947 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν (S=O)¹¹. On complexation through oxygen it is shifted to the lower frequency region due to a decrease in the π character of S=O bond and appears at 900 cm⁻¹.

Adducts of S-donor ligands:

TMTS: In tetramethylthiouramdisulphide, the ν (C-N) undergoes positive shift (1225 to 1238 cm⁻¹) showing absence of coordination through nitrogen. The C=S stretching mode of very strong intensity appearing at 970 cm⁻¹ in the pure base undergoes a slightly positive shift (980 cm⁻¹) on complexation indicating indirectly coordination through sulphur of the C-S¹¹.

2-atz: The C-N frequency is shifted to higher frequency on complexation, suggesting absence of coordination through nitrogen. The ν (C-S) in the free ligand appears at 700 cm⁻¹ and is shifted to

667 cm⁻¹ indicating bonding through sulphur of the base¹¹.

btz, 2-abtz: $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{CN}) + \delta(\text{N-C-S})$ shifts from 1450 in btz to 1460 cm⁻¹ in the adducts, indicating the absence of coordination through the nitrogen atom of the ligand and indirectly suggesting Ti←S bonding.

In case of 2-abtz adducts the band of the free ligand at 1641, 1523, 1444 cm⁻¹ are shifted to 1637, 1595, 1460 cm⁻¹, respectively. These bands correspond to the stretching mode of particular bands or to the conjugated mode of the thiazole ring in the complex¹².

Adducts of sulphadrugs (sulphaguanidine, sulphadiazine, sulphamethaxazole):

Sulphaguanidine and sulphadiazine show δ NH₂ band around 1640 cm⁻¹ which on complexation is shifted to lower frequencies of 1610 and 1580 cm⁻¹, respectively confirming the involvement of the NH₂ of the anilino group in coordination¹².

In the case of sulphamethaxazole, the δ NH₂ band shows positive shift on complexation, 1610 in the free ligand to 1620 cm⁻¹ in the complex, indicating absence of coordination through the NH₂ of anilino group. The C-O frequency in methylisazole observed at 1150 cm⁻¹ is shifted to higher frequency at 1160 cm⁻¹ on complexation. This positive shift in ν CO is due to the tilting of the ring on complexation and is indicative of bonding through the oxygen of the isazole ring.

Mixed ligands adducts: The characteristic peaks of the two different ligands found in the adducts show coordination through the donor sites of both the ligands.

DMSO, β -pic: The ν (S=O) shifts from 1045 to 990 cm⁻¹ and ν (C=N) from 1550 to 1620 cm⁻¹ confirming bonding through oxygen of DMSO and nitrogen of β -pic.

Bu₂SO, β -pic: The ν (S=O) in Bu₂SO is observed at 947 cm⁻¹ and is shifted to 910 cm⁻¹. The ν (C=N) appears at 1610 from 1550 cm⁻¹ of β -pic. Both these shifts indicate that both the ligands are coordinated to titanium.

Bu₂SO, btz: The ν (S=O) on complexation is shifted from 947 to 910 cm⁻¹. $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{CN}) + \delta(\text{N-C-S})$ is shifted from 1450 to 1453 showing absence of bonding through the nitrogen atom of the ligand and indirectly suggest Ti←S bonding. This observation confirms that both the ligands take part in bonding.

btz, DMSO: The ν (S=O) on complexation is shifted from 1045 to 900 cm⁻¹. $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{CN}) + \delta(\text{N-C-S})$ is shifted from 1450 to 1463 cm⁻¹ on complexation suggesting indirectly Ti←S bonding. Thus the oxygen of DMSO and sulphur of btz take part in complexation.

4-picO, 2-atz: The ν NO of 4-picO is shifted from 1250 to 1210 cm⁻¹ on complexation. The δ NH₂ is shifted to lower region from 1620 to 1612

cm⁻¹ on complexation showing bonding through exocyclic nitrogen of 2-atz. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ show a slight positive shift on complexation and indicate the absence of bonding through sulphur or nitrogen of the 2-atz ring. Thus the bonding in the mixed ligands complex occurs through oxygen of 4-picO and exocyclic nitrogen of 2-atz.

PMR Spectra : The pmr spectrum of adduct of TiCl_4 with 1-Me-2-piper shows singlet at 7.15 τ due to methyl protons and a triplet at 6.8 τ , 7.55 τ showing three types of methylene protons of the ligand.

The pmr spectrum of the mixed ligands adduct of TiCl_4 with Bu_2SO and β -pic shows singlet at 7.81 τ due to methyl protons and a multiplet in the range of 1.79-2.58 τ due to phenyl protons of β -pic. The multiplet centered around 7.17 τ and 9.5 τ is attributed to the butyl protons of Bu_2SO .

The spectra and their integration are consistent with the proposed stoichiometry of both the adducts.

Assessment of plant growth regulating capacity :

The data of the screening results are presented in Table 3. Taking into account the length of the plants only, the statistical calculations based on analysis of variance method¹⁴, using completely randomized design (C.R.D.) are done as follows and the results are presented in Anova Tables 4a, b and c.

Degree of freedom of treatment = $n - 1$ (where n = number treatment/replication)

Degree of replication = $n - 1$

and Degree of freedom of error = (degree of freedom of treatment) $\times$ (degree of freedom of replication).

TABLE 4

ANOVA-TABLE a

Source of variation	d. f.	S. S.	M. S. S.	F. Cal.	F. tab
Treatment	4	50.6960	12.659	0.45	F(4,16) at 5%
Replication	4	59.028	14.757		3.01
Error	16	446.976	27.936		↓
Total	24	556.64			Ho. accepted

ANOVA-TABLE b

Source of variation	d. f.	S. S.	M. S. S.	F. Cal.	F. tab
Treatment	4	347.8856	86.9714	1.69	3.01
Replication	4	400.7696	100.1924		↓
Error	16	820.9624	51.3103		Ho. accepted
Total	24	1569.6176			

ANOVA-TABLE c

Source of variation	d. f.	S. S.	M. S. S.	F. Cal.	F. tab
Treatment	4	493.53	120.8825	2.32	3.01
Replication	4	383.34	95.8355		↓
Error	16	831.074	51.9421		Ho. accepted
Total	24	1697.94600			

d. f. = Degree of freedom, S. S. = Sum of square, M. S. S. = Mean of sum of square, F = Variation ratio.

$$\text{Total sum of squares} = \text{T.S.S.} = \sum Y_i^2 - \frac{G^2}{N} \dots \text{(I)}$$

[where $\sum Y_i^2$ = (total sum of the square of the length of each plant) ; $\frac{G^2}{N}$ = correction = C (G = total sum of each plant length ; N = number of total plants)].

Sum of square of treatment = S.S.T.

$$= \frac{\sum T_i^2}{5} - C \dots \text{(II)}$$

TABLE 3—SCREENING TABLE FOR PLANT GROWTH

	A	A ₁	A ¹	B	B ₁	B ¹	C	C ₁	C ¹	D	D ₁	D ¹	E	E ₁	E ¹
1.	*12.8 †(8)	18.6 (11)	18.7 (13)	18.8 (10)	30.5 (13)	32.9 (15)	8.5 (5)	8.8 (6)	9.1 (7)	19.0 (9)	22.2 (11)	24.0 (15)	21.9 (11)	27.1 (13)	29.8 (16)
2.	10.0 (6)	15.6 (9)	16.2 (12)	19.7 (10)	32.5 (14)	36.5 (16)	18.8 (10)	30.7 (13)	32.2 (16)	14.0 (7)	22.7 (10)	23.2 (13)	14.5 (7)	35.3 (14)	35.5 (16)
3.	26.6 (9)	42.6 (14)	43.2 (16)	16.8 (9)	34.7 (14)	34.7 (15)	15.5 (8)	33.2 (14)	33.8 (15)	19.5 (10)	33.0 (12)	35.5 (13)	17.9 (9)	26.9 (12)	28.4 (13)
4.	13.2 (8)	23.8 (14)	25.6 (14)	14.2 (9)	29.0 (16)	29.0 (16)	16.5 (8)	17.7 (12)	17.8 (12)	22.0 (9)	22.0 (14)	35.5 (15)	41.4 (9)	18.0 (15)	32.6 (16)
5.	10.5 (7)	33.2 (11)	24.7 (13)	23.3 (9)	41.3 (14)	41.3 (14)	23.5 (11)	25.8 (13)	25.8 (13)	18.5 (10)	35.5 (14)	35.5 (15)	9.0 (6)	21.6 (10)	26.1 (12)

A, B, C, D, E = Group of plants containing five plants in each group.

* Length of the plant in cm. † Number of nodes of the plant in brackets.

A = untreated

B = treated with TiCl_4 .SG

C = treated with SG

D = treated with TiCl_4 .SD

E = treated with SD

A, A₁, A¹ = Length of the plant in the initial stage, on the 14th day and on the 21st day, respectively.

where T_1 = total sum of the length of plants of each treatment.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sum of square of replication} &\approx \text{S.S.R.} \\ &= \frac{\sum R_i^2}{5} - C \end{aligned} \quad \dots \text{ (III)}$$

where R_i = total sum of the length of the plants of each replication.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Since sum of square of error} \\ &= \text{S.S.E.} = \text{T.S.S.} - \text{S.S.T.} - \text{S.S.R.} \end{aligned}$$

and F Cal. = variance ratio

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{\text{Mean sum of square of treatment}}{\text{Mean sum of square of error}} \\ &= \frac{\text{M.S.S.T.}}{\text{M.S.S.E.}} \quad (\text{Mean of sum of square} = \text{M.S.S.}) \\ &= \frac{\text{S.S.}}{\text{df}} \quad \text{where, S.S.} = \text{sum of square ; d.f.} = \text{degree of} \end{aligned}$$

freedom).

F Cal. could be calculated.

Now from the literature¹⁴

$$\begin{aligned} F(4, 16) \text{ tab.} &= 3.01 \\ &5\% \end{aligned}$$

[where 4 = d.f. of treatment/replication ; 16 = d.f. of error ; 5% = with permissible error of 5%].

Null hypothesis = H_0 = the differences are not significant.

From Anova Tables 4a, b and c it is apparent that F Cal. is always less than F tab. Therefore H_0 is accepted i.e. the effect of the compounds on the growth of the plant is not significant.

For the sake of brevity the calculations taking the nodes into account have not been given as they do not affect the conclusions made through the above calculations.

It is found from the analytical spectral data that titanium is hexacoordinated except in the case

of DEA, TMTS, BipyO_2 , 2-atz, SD, SZ where it is pentacoordinated. The adduct of SG and SD have no significant effect on the growth of the plant.

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